

Association between ABO Blood Group Salivary Secretor Status and Urinary Infection

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Abstract

Women experience urinary tract infections more frequently. Most often, they affect the bladder or urethra, but more severe infections affect the kidney. The relationship between the secretor status of the ABO and Rh blood groups and urinary tract infections was assessed since a bladder infection can also result in pelvic pain, increased urogenital tract pain, pain during urination, and blood in the urine. A total of 200 male and female participants with urinary tract infections, aged 30 to 60, were chosen for the research. They were split into two groups: 100 subjects who were healthy and did not appear to have a urinary tract infection served as the control group, and 100 subjects who had a urinary tract infection were proven to have one. The slide agglutination method was used to detect the ABO and Rh blood groups, and the Haemagglutination Inhibition technique was used to assess whether or not saliva contained water-soluble ABH blood group antigens. Out of 100 Urinary tract infections participants, 70 were secretors and 30 were non secretors and out of 100 non Urinary tract infections subjects, 89 were secretors and 11 were non secretors. Urinary tract infections and secretor status did not show a statistically significant connection ($p < 0.05$). Moreover, there was a strong correlation ($p < 0.05$) between urinary tract infections and AB blood group non-secretors. This study probably revealed that the non-secretors of AB blood type were more prone to Urinary tract infections.

Keywords: Urinary tract infections, ABH antigen, secretor, non-secretors and ABO and Rh blood group.

Introduction

The term "secretor status" describes whether or not an individual's body fluids such as tears, saliva, breast milk, urine, and semen contain water-soluble ABO blood group antigens. A person is called a secretor if they secrete these antigens in their body fluids; a non-secretor does not. The FUT2 gene, also known as the Se gene, regulates secretor status [1]. The secretor phenotype is inherited autosomally dominantly and is displayed by those who have at least one functional copy of the gene. The trait known as the non-secretor phenotype (se) is inherited. ABH secretors are those that secrete blood group antigens in bodily fluids such saliva, sweat, tears, semen, and serum; non-secretors are those who do not secrete blood type antigens in bodily fluids. The autosomal dominant secretor gene (fucosyltransferase 2) is controlled by two alleles, dominant (Se) and recessive (se) [2].

Individuals with homozygous recessive secretors and non-secretors, respectively, are individuals who carry the dominant gene and are homozygous heterozygous (SeSe/Sese). The absence of blood type antigens in physiological secretions is seen as a drawback since it makes people more sensitive to certain ailments, such as Urinary tract infections [3]

Every infection in any area of the urinary system is referred to as a urinary tract infection (UTI). The bladder, urethra, ureters, and kidneys make up the urinary system. Most infections affect the bladder and urethra, which are parts of the lower urinary system [4].

The chance of getting a UTI is higher in women than in men. It can be uncomfortable and unpleasant if an infection is restricted to the bladder. On the other hand, if a UTI spreads to the kidneys, it can cause grave health issues. Urinary tract infections are a prevalent issue among females. Around 50% of women are predicted to experience at least one urinary

tract infection throughout their lifetime. There are antibacterial drugs with good in vitro activity available, however many women still have infections again [5]. There have been suggestions that this issue is caused by a breakdown in the host defenses. Despite the fact that simple lower urinary tract infections seldom cause kidney damage. Renal damage may arise from upper urinary tract infections. Most young children who experience scarring after urinary tract infections are younger than five years old. This is the age range where the child's immune system is still developing and the mother's antibody has decreased. Additionally, bacterial meningitis is most common in this age range [6].

The higher percentage of non-secretors in Urinary tract infections patients indicated that blood group antigen secretion may contribute to the host's innate defenses against infection during this susceptible time [7].

But secretors have been reported to be more susceptible to infections caused by Urinary tract infections as opposed to non-secretors. Urinary tract infections are largely genetically driven, and has has a stronger association with ancestry and family history. Additionally, race and environmental factors might be important [8]. Because the salivary secretor status of the ABO blood type is also genetically defined, hence the connection between Urinary tract infections and secretor status are evaluated.

Materials and method

Patients with a diagnosis of urinary tract infection participated in the current analytical case control study, which was conducted at Specialist Hospital Umuguma. Two hundred male and female participants, aged between thirty and sixty, were chosen for the research. The control group and the urinary tract infection comprised the two groups of study participants. From the institutional ethical committee, ethical clearance was acquired.

Determination of the Rh and ABO blood groups the slide agglutination method was used to identify the Rh and ABO blood groups.

Principle: The agglutination concept serves as the foundation for the antisera technique. Normal human red blood cells that have antigens on them clump together when the appropriate antibody is present. An ABO blood type was ascertained using Anti-A and Anti-B sera. By applying a single drop of Anti-D serum to a spotless glass slide, the Rh factor was ascertained. One drop of whole blood was added to Anti-D Sera using a Pasteur pipette. The cell-serum combination was thoroughly blended with the use of an applicator stick. The slide was tipped back and forth, and agglutination was watched for. Tests that demonstrated agglutination within two minutes were deemed Rh positive; those that did not were deemed Rh negative.

Determination of secretor and non-secretor status

water-soluble ABH blood type antigens and their presence or absence in a person's body fluids, such as saliva. The Haemagglutination Inhibition Technique was used to identify the subjects in each group after the determination was made.

Principle of the Haemagglutination Inhibition Technique

The blood type specific material ABH antigen is present in a water soluble form. When this substance is produced in secretions like saliva, it can precisely neutralize its corresponding antibody. This is advantageous. The agglutinin titer is completely or partially inhibited as a result of this neutralization. This is the inhibition technique's foundation.

Interpretations

The presence of agglutination under the microscope is indicated as non-secretor; the absence of agglutination under the microscope is indicated as secretor.

Reagents: For participants of blood types A, B, or AB, antisera A and antisera B of human origin were utilized. The Anti-H lectin was employed for the subjects in group "O." Blood samples were taken in anticoagulant test tubes from groups A, B, and O. Shortly before the test, a 3% suspension of red blood cells was made.

Collection and processing of saliva

The subjects of both the groups were requested to rinse the mouth with antiseptic mouthwash and about 5ml of saliva was collected in a dry test tube with all precautions not to allow it to get mixed with water. The tube was submerged in a bath of boiling water for ten minutes right away. This eliminated salivary amylase, an enzyme that would have normally impacted antigen activity and produced erroneous positive agglutination results. Following the heating of the saliva, the tube was centrifuged for approximately ten minutes at a speed of 2000 revolutions per minute. After being separated, the supernatant fluid was refrigerated until the testing date. On the same day that they were collected, every saliva sample was evaluated. At room temperature (between 250 and 270 C), every sample was examined.

Results

Out of 100 Urinary tract infections subjects, 70 were secretors and 30 were non secretors and out of 100 non Urinary tract infections subjects, 89 were secretors and 11 were non secretors.

Table1: Association of secretor status with Urinary track infection

Secretor status	Control Group	Percentage (%)	Urinary track infection	Percentage (%)
Non secretor	11	26.83%	30	73.17%
Secretor	89	55.97	70	44.03%
Total	100	50%	100	50%

Table 2: Association of Secretor Status in Control and Urinary tract infection with ABO Blood Group

Blood group	Control group				Urinary track infection			
	Secretor	%	Non secretor	%	Secretor	%	Non Secretor	%
A	15	55.6%	03	30.0%	12	44.4%	07	70.0%
B	16	44.4%	03	23.1%	20	74.1%	10	76.9%
AB	42	62.7%	03	15%	25	37.3%	17	85%
O	16	66.2%	02	25%	13	55.3%	06	75%

Discussion

An ABH secretor is a person who secretes ABO blood group antigens into bodily fluids such as saliva, perspiration, tears, semen, and serum. Secretors make up almost 80% of the population. Non-secretors are those who do not release their blood type antigen. Approximately 20% of the population are not secretors. Since the discovery of these antigens, significant attempts have been made to determine whether ABO (H) antigens and a variety of illnesses are positively correlated [9].

The percentage of urinary tract infection non-secretors was higher than that of control group, while the percentage of urinary tract infection secretors was higher than that of control group. However, statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between urinary tract infection and secretor status [10]. Urinary tract infection has previously been linked to non-secretors [11].

The current investigation found that the urinary tract infection had a higher non-secretor of AB blood group than the control group. This is a positive correlation between AB blood group urinary tract infections and non secretors. In the AB blood group, this indicates that non-secretors were found to be more susceptible to urinary tract infections. yet, compared to the controls in blood group A, the number of O and B secretors was higher in the urinary tract infection; yet, the difference between them was not statistically significant. Lack of innate defense mechanisms and local immunity is one risk factor for the development of urinary tract infection in non-secretors. The association between ABO blood types and the secretor status of control and urinary tract infection individuals is still up for debate [12].

In each blood group, it was discovered that a greater proportion of patients with urinary tract infections were non-secretors than controls. This aligns with the findings of the conducted research [13].

Shown by [14], which claims that those who are Lewis negative and ABH non-secretors are more likely to get urinary tract infections and may also be more likely to experience consequences from such infections.

Conclusion

The non-secretors of the AB blood type exhibited a noteworthy distinction and were more vulnerable to urinary tract infections, according to the present study. The study did not, however, find a connection between the ABO blood type and urinary tract infection.

References

1. Kinane, D. F., Blackwell, C. C., Winstanley, F. P., & Weir, D. M. (1983). Blood group, secretor status, and susceptibility to infection by *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*. *Sexually Transmitted Infections*, 59(1), 44-46.
2. Medina, M., & Castillo-Pino, E. (2019). An introduction to the epidemiology and burden of urinary tract infections. *Therapeutic advances in urology*, 11, 1756287219832172.
3. Heggelund, J. E., Varrot, A., Imberty, A., & Kregel, U. (2017). Histo-blood group antigens as mediators of infections. *Current opinion in structural biology*, 44, 190-200.
4. Cooling L (2015). Blood Groups in Infection and Host Susceptibility. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 28(3):801 -70
5. Weiss, F. U., Schurmann, C., Teumer, A., Mayerle, J., Simon, P., Völzke, H., ... & Lerch, M. M. (2016). ABO blood type B and fucosyltransferase 2 non-secretor status as genetic risk factors for chronic pancreatitis. *Gut*, 65(2), 353-354.
6. Harris, J. B., & LaRocque, R. C. (2016). Cholera and ABO blood group: understanding an ancient association. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*, 95(2), 263.
7. Alzahran M, Jawdat D, Alaskar A, Cereb N, Hajeer AH (2018). ABO and Rh blood group genotypes in a cohort of Saudi stem cell donors. *Int J Immunogenet*. 45.2: 63 -64.
8. Etim, E. A., Akpotuzor, J. O., Ohwonigho, A. C., & Francis, A. A. (2017). Distribution of ABO and Rhesus blood groups among selected tribes in Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Hematol Transfus Int J*, 4(6), 149-152.
9. Kinane, D. F., Blackwell, C. C., Weir, D. M., Winstanley, F. P., & Elton, R. A. (1983). ABO blood groups and susceptibility to gonococcal infection. III. Role of isohemagglutinins in increased association of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* to monocytes from blood group B individuals. *Journal of clinical & laboratory immunology*, 12(2), 83-86.
10. Franchini, M., & Bonfanti, C. (2015). Evolutionary aspects of ABO blood group in humans. *Clinica chimica acta*, 444, 66-71.
11. Källenius, G., Möllby, R., Svenson, S. B., Winberg, J., Lundblad, A., Svensson, S., & Cedergren, B. (1980). The Pk antigen as receptor for the haemagglutinin of pyelonephritic *Escherichia coli*. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 7(4), 297-302.
12. Pardeshi, P. (2018). Prevalence of urinary tract infections and current scenario of antibiotic susceptibility pattern of bacteria causing UTI. *Indian Journal of Microbiology Research*, 5(3), 334-338.
13. Maraki, S., Samonis, G., Rafailidis, P. I., Vouloumanou, E. K., Mavromanolakis, E., & Falagas, M. E. (2009). Susceptibility of urinary tract bacteria to fosfomycin. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*, 53(10), 4508-4510.